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Pell-Lucas-Galerkin method for solving two-classes of fractional optimal control problems

Zahra Najafi^{1*}, Yadollah Ordokhani¹, Sedigheh Sabermahani²

¹Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematical Sciences, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran.

²Department of Mathematics Education, Farhangian University, Tehran, Iran.

z.najafi@alzahra.ac.ir, ordokhani@alzahra.ac.ir, s.saber@cfu.ac.ir

Abstract. The aim of this work is to present a new computational scheme to solve two classes of fractional optimal control problems by using Pell-Lucas polynomials and Galerkin method. Here, we present operational matrices of fractional integration and pantograph for Pell-Lucas polynomials. Then, these matrices and the Galerkin method are used to convert the considered problems to systems of algebraic equations. The applicability of the proposed method is demonstrated by numerical examples.

1. Introduction

We Consider the following functional:

$$\min \mathcal{J} = \int_0^1 f(t, x(t), u(t)) dt, \tag{1}$$

subject to the following dynamical systems [2, 4]:

• **Case 1:**

$$\begin{cases} D^\nu x(t) = g_1(t, x(t), u(t)), & t \in [0, 1]. \\ x^{(i)}(0) = \mu_i, & i = 0, 1, \dots, \lceil \nu \rceil - 1. \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

*Speaker

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- **Case 2:**

$$\begin{cases} D^\nu x(t) = g_2(t, x(t), x(qt), u(t)), & t \in [0, 1]. \\ x^{(i)}(0) = \mu_i, & i = 0, 1, \dots, \lceil \nu \rceil - 1. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In both of the mentioned cases, D^ν denotes the Caputo fractional derivative which is defined in [4]. Fractional optimal control problems are an important class of problems that have various phenomena can be effectively modeled by different types of them. In this paper, a new numerical method based on Pell-Lucas polynomials and Galerkin method is proposed to solve fractional optimal control problems and pantograph fractional optimal control problems. Also, we introduce operational matrices of fractional integration and pantograph for the Pell-Lucas polynomials.

2. Pell-Lucas polynomials and function approximation

- Pell-Lucas polynomials are given by the following relation [1]:

$$Q_0(t) = 2, \quad Q_i(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} \frac{i}{i-k} \binom{i-k}{k} (2t)^{i-2k} \quad (i \geq 1). \quad (4)$$

- An arbitrary function $f(t) \in L^2[0, 1]$ can be expressed using $Q_i(t), i = 0, 1, \dots, M$ as the following form:

$$f(t) \simeq \sum_{i=0}^M c_i Q_i(t) = C^T Q(t), \quad (5)$$

where, C and $Q(t)$ are $(M+1) \times 1$ vectors, given by, $C = [c_0, c_1, \dots, c_M]^T$ and $Q(t) = [Q_0(t), Q_1(t), \dots, Q_M(t)]^T$. We obtain the coefficient vector C as follows:

$$C = D^{-1} \langle f(t), Q(t) \rangle, \quad (6)$$

where

$$D = \langle Q(t), Q(t) \rangle = \int_0^1 Q(t) Q(t)^T dt. \quad (7)$$

3. The operational matrix of fractional-order integral

By applying the fractional integration operator [3] on $Q(t)$, we can obtain the desired operational matrix in which $I^\nu Q(t) \simeq P Q(t)$, and P is the operational matrix of fractional-order integral in $(M+1) \times (M+1)$ order. For $i = 0$:

$$I^\nu Q_0(t) = I^\nu(2) = \frac{2}{\Gamma(1+\nu)} t^\nu \simeq \sum_{s=0}^M \frac{2}{\Gamma(1+\nu)} c_s Q_s(t), \quad (8)$$

where, c_s is calculated by Eq. (6). Then we obtain:

$$I^\nu Q_0(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2}{\Gamma(1+\nu)} c_0 & \frac{2}{\Gamma(1+\nu)} c_1 & \dots & \frac{2}{\Gamma(1+\nu)} c_M \end{bmatrix} Q(t) = P_0 Q(t), \quad (9)$$

For $i = 1, 2, \dots, M$, we have:

$$I^\nu Q_i(t) = I^\nu \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} \frac{i}{i-k} \binom{i-k}{k} (2t)^{i-2k} \right) = \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} \frac{i}{i-k} \binom{i-k}{k} I^\nu ((2t)^{i-2k}). \quad (10)$$

Also, we can write:

$$I^\nu Q_i(t) \simeq \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} b_{i,k} t^{(i-2k)+\nu}, \quad b_{i,k} = \frac{i}{i-k} \binom{i-k}{k} 2^{(i-2k)} \frac{\Gamma(i-2k+1)}{\Gamma(i-2k+1+\nu)}. \quad (11)$$

We can expand $t^{(i-2k)+\nu}$ in terms of Pell-Lucas polynomials as $t^{(i-2k)+\nu} \simeq \sum_{s=0}^M c_{k,s} Q_s(t)$. Then, we get:

$$I^\nu Q_i(t) \simeq \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} b_{i,k} \sum_{s=0}^M c_{k,s} Q_s(t) = \sum_{s=0}^M \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} b_{i,k} c_{k,s} \right) Q_s(t). \quad (12)$$

Let $a_{i,s,k} = b_{i,k} c_{k,s}$ and we obtain for $i = 1, 2, \dots, M$:

$$I^\nu Q_i(t) \simeq \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} a_{i,0,k} \quad \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} a_{i,1,k} \quad \dots \quad \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} a_{i,M,k} \right] Q(t) = P_i Q(t), \quad (13)$$

and $P = [P_i]$ for $i = 0, 1, \dots, M$.

4. Pantograph operational matrix

For $0 < q < 1$ and $0 \leq t \leq 1$, we have:

$$Q(qt) \simeq D_q Q(t), \quad (14)$$

where D_q is the pantograph operational matrix of Pell-Lucas polynomials. For $i = 0$, we have $Q_0(qt) = Q_0(t) = 2$, then we can write $Q_0(qt) = [1, 0, \dots, 0]Q(t)$. By using the same process in Sect.(3) and changing variable t to qt in Eq. (4), for $i = 1, 2, \dots, M$, we have:

$$Q_i(qt) \simeq \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} \tilde{a}_{i,0,k} \quad \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} \tilde{a}_{i,1,k} \quad \dots \quad \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor} \tilde{a}_{i,M,k} \right] Q(t), \quad (15)$$

where, $\tilde{a}_{i,s,k} = \tilde{b}_{i,k} \tilde{c}_{k,s}$, $\tilde{b}_{i,k} = \frac{i}{i-k} \binom{i-k}{k} (2q)^{(i-2k)}$ and $\tilde{c}_{k,s}$ are coefficients that obtain from expanding t^{i-2k} that are calculated by Eq. (6).

5. Numerical Method

We use Pell-Lucas polynomials to extend $D^\nu x(t)$ and $u(t)$ in case 1 and case 2. We let, $D^\nu x(t) \simeq X^T Q(t)$, $u(t) \simeq U^T Q(t)$ that X and U are unknown vector. By applying I^ν and by using properties of the operator I^ν [4] on above equations, we can write for two cases in problem (1):

$$x(t) \simeq I^\nu (X^T Q(t)) = X^T P Q(t) + \sum_{i=0}^{[\nu]-1} \mu_i \frac{t^i}{i!} = (X^T P + E^T) Q(t). \quad (16)$$

Also, we compute the integration (1), by using Eq.(7) simply. On the other hand, we insert the mentioned approximations in case 1 and case 2, then we get:

• **Case 1:**

$$\Lambda_1(t) := X^T Q(t) - g_1 \left(t, (X^T P + E^T) Q(t), U^T Q(t) \right), \quad (17)$$

• **Case 2:**

$$\Lambda_2(t) := X^T Q(t) - g_2 \left(t, (X^T P + E^T) Q(t), (X^T P + E^T) D_q Q(t), U^T Q(t) \right), \quad (18)$$

By applying the Galerkin method, the above relations transform to the following relations:

$$\hat{\Lambda}_i(t) = \langle \Lambda_i(t), Q(t) \rangle, \quad i = 1, 2. \quad (19)$$

Then we have for case 1, $\mathcal{J}_1^* = \mathcal{J} + \hat{\Lambda}_1 \lambda$, and for case 2, $\mathcal{J}_2^* = \mathcal{J} + \hat{\Lambda}_2 \lambda$, where λ is the unknown Lagrange multiplier's vector with the appropriate dimension. The following equations must be held in order to find extremum of \mathcal{J}_i^* , for $i = 1, 2$.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}_i^*}{\partial X} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}_i^*}{\partial U} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}_i^*}{\partial \lambda} = 0, \quad i = 1, 2. \quad (20)$$

Finally, we use the "linsolve" package in Matlab to solve the algebraic systems of equations. Moreover, we compute the approximate values of $x(t)$ and $u(t)$ in each case.

6. Numerical examples

Example 6.1. Consider the following fractional optimal control problem:

$$\min \quad \mathcal{J} = \int_0^1 [0.625x^2(t) + 0.5u^2(t) + 0.5u(t)x(t)] dt,$$

s.t.

$$D^\nu x(t) = 0.5x(t) + u(t), \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1, \quad 0 < \nu \leq 1,$$

$$x(0) = 1.$$

The exact solutions for this problem with $\nu = 1$ are $x(t) = \frac{\cosh(1-t)}{\cosh(1)}$, $u(t) = \frac{-(\tanh(1-t)+0.5)\cosh(1-t)}{\cosh(1)}$ and $\mathcal{J} \simeq 0.380797078$. Table 1, shows the approximate values of functional \mathcal{J} using the proposed method, Boubaker polynomials [3] and Fibonacci wavelets method [4] for $\nu = 1$. Figure 1 illustrates the curves of the approximated variables, $x(t)$ and $u(t)$ for $M = 4$ and different values of ν .

TABLE 1. Comparison between our method and other methods for approximated value of \mathcal{J} for $\nu = 1$ in Example 6.1.

Method	\mathcal{J}
Boubaker polynomials($m = 5$)	0.380797
Fibonacci wavelets method ($M = 4, k = 1$)	0.380797070
Our method ($M = 3$)	0.380797078
Exact value	0.380797078

FIGURE 1. The curves of the approximated variables, $x(t)$ and $u(t)$ for $M = 4$ and different values of ν in Example 6.1.

TABLE 2. Numerical results for $\nu = 1$ and different values of M in Example 6.2.

Exact value	$M = 4$	$M = 5$	$M = 6$
-0.28090533251181	-0.28090533249271	-0.28090533251178	-0.28090533251181

Example 6.2. Consider the following fractional optimal control problem [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \mathcal{J} = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 [x^2(t) - 2e^{-t}x(t) + u^2(t) + e^{-\frac{3}{4}t}u(t)] dt, \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \\ & D^\nu x(t) = \frac{1}{2}x\left(\frac{3}{4}t\right) - x(t) + u(t), \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1, \quad 0 < \nu \leq 1, \\ & x(0) = 1. \end{aligned}$$

The optimal solutions are $x(t) = e^{-t}$ and $u(t) = -\frac{1}{2}e^{-\frac{3}{4}t}$ when $\nu = 1$. Table 2 shows the numerical results for $\nu = 1$ and different values of M . The plots of absolute errors for $x(t)$ and $u(t)$ in $\nu = 1$ and $M = 5$ are shown in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2. The plots of absolute errors for $x(t)$ and $u(t)$ in $\nu = 1$ and $M = 5$ for Example 6.2.

7. Conclusion

Herein, we presented a numerical method for solving two classes of fractional optimal control problems. The scheme is developed by fractional integration and pantograph operational matrices and Galerkin method. Moreover, the numerical illustrative examples showed the efficiency and validity of this proposed method.

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